

Tetravalent Nickel : Molecular Design, Chemistry and Cyclic Voltammetry

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The possibility of obtaining stable octahedral nickel(IV) species using appropriate ligand design is explored. Studied with the help of an indigenously built cyclic voltammeter, the oxidation-reduction reactions of such species have revealed; (i) the occurrence of coupled electron and proton transfer reactions, (ii) the formation of nickel(III) intermediates under certain conditions and (iii) the occurrence of irreversible decomposition after reversible electron transfer. The various electrode processes have been characterized thermodynamically. The rate of the decomposition reaction is also determined. The oximate group plays the dual role of stabilizing high oxidation states and of providing a pathway for facile electron transfer.

INORGANIC chemists have long been fascinated¹ by uncommon oxidation states of elements, transition elements in particular. In the case of nickel, the common oxidation state is nickel(II). The higher oxidation states, nickel(III) and nickel(IV) are relatively rare. The very limited number of genuine nickel(IV) species include¹⁻⁶ σ -complexes having NiN_6 , NiO_6 , NiF_6 , $NiAs_4X_2$, NiP_4X_2 , NiS_6 and $NiSe_6$ coordination spheres and π -complexes derived from cyclopentadienyl, dicarbollide and related species. It is appropriate here to make a special mention of the works⁷⁻⁹ of Professor P. Ray on periodates and molybdates of nickel(IV). For sometime we have been interested in the design of discrete molecular systems in which nickel is stabilized in the tetravalent state. As the work progressed we had to enter deep into electrochemical aspects of the problem. The major features of our research are reviewed here. Some of the results have already been published⁹⁻¹².

Results and Discussion

A. Molecular Design

It has been postulated¹³ that high oxidation states of nickel are favoured by localized accumulation of negative charge on donor atoms and formation of strong metal-ligand σ bonds. Oximate anions satisfy well the requirement of negative charge and a nitrogen based coordination sphere can provide the necessary strong metal-ligand σ interaction. Since hexadentate ligands will generally yield thermodynamically stable octahedral complexes, we concentrated our initial attention on such ligands. We hoped that by this choice, we shall be able to get nickel(II) and nickel(IV) systems both of which will be sufficiently stable to allow a study of their chemical and electrochemical interconversions unhindered by decomposition. The ligand system I is readily obtained by condensing an isonitrosoketone with triethylenetetramine. For the sake of brevity the present discussion will be limited to the case $R=R'=Me$. This ligand will be abbreviated as H_2L where the protons are those on the oxime functions. This ligand was recently reported by Russian workers who

described¹⁴⁻¹⁶ cobalt(III) and copper(II) complexes.

The brown crystalline nickel(II) complex $Ni(H_2L)X_2$ ($X=ClO_4, NO_3$) is readily obtained by reacting H_2L with NiX_2 . It is fully paramagnetic (3.12 BM at 30°C) and behaves as a 1 : 2 electrolyte (Table 1). Its electronic spectrum is strongly suggestive of a pseudo-octahedral ligand field with $Dq \sim 1300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. $Ni(H_2L)^{2+}$ belongs to the structural type II which has been shown¹⁵ to be present in cobalt(III) complexes of H_2L by the X-ray diffraction technique.

When $Ni(H_2L)(ClO_4)_2$ is suspended in concentrated HNO_3 at room temperature, the solid progressively dissolves, nitrous fumes are evolved and a deep red solution results. On dilution of the reaction mixture followed by cooling, dark violet crystals of composition $Ni(L)(ClO_4)_2$ deposit in good yield. This compound is indefinitely stable in vacuum, but in moist atmosphere it progressively change colour until an orange-brown solid is left which is identical with $Ni(H_2L)(ClO_4)_2$. When an aqueous solution of $Ni(L)(ClO_4)_2$ is boiled, it is quantitatively converted to $Ni(H_2L)(ClO_4)_2$. Aqueous $Ni(L)(ClO_4)_2$ instantly oxidizes many reducing agents. The reaction with Fe^{2+} was studied quantitatively. Two moles of Fe^{2+} are consumed per mole of $Ni(L)(ClO_4)_2$ and the reaction is,

These experiments demonstrate that no fundamental change in the ligand backbone occurs during concentrated HNO_3 oxidation of $Ni(H_2L)(ClO_4)_2$.

Ni(L)(ClO₄)₂ is diamagnetic and behaves as an 1:2 electrolyte in solution (Table 1). All data taken collectively strongly suggest that Ni(L)(ClO₄)₂ contain nickel in the oxidation state four, held in an NiN₆ core of structural type II. Certain observations are pertinent in this context. With metal (II), the species M(H₂L)²⁺ (M = Ni, Fe) is readily obtained in aqueous solution; appreciable proton dissociation occurs only on addition of alkali (*vide infra*). As expected such dissociation becomes more facile in metal (III) complexes, e. g., Co(H₂L)³⁺. This trend should continue and proton dissociation should become even more facile in going to a metal (IV) complex. Indeed the protonated species Ni(HL)³⁺ or Ni(H₂L)⁴⁺ have not been isolated; only Ni(L)²⁺ obtains even in strongly acidic solutions.

TABLE 1—SOME CHARACTERIZATION DATA (298°K)

Data	Ni(H ₂ L)(ClO ₄) ₂	Ni(L)(ClO ₄) ₂
1. Electrical conductivity in intramethane (ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	143	137
2. Magnetic Moment (BM)	3.12	Diamagnetic
3. Electronic spectrum in aqueous solution (cm ⁻¹ (lit mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹))	12,820(40); 20,000(75)	20,000(6300) 23,260(6000)
4. Infrared spectrum (cm ⁻¹)	NH 3300 OH 3300 diimine 1670; 1600	3200 — 1610, 1500

We suspect that the negative charge on oximate oxygen plays an important role in partial neutralization of the excess positive charge on the metal ion through inductive transmission and *sigma* donation. For stability such redistribution of charge is necessary (electroneutrality principle).

B. Charge Transfer Characteristics

A comparative study of the electronic and infrared spectra of the isoelectronic (d⁶) iron(II), cobalt(III) and nickel(IV) complexes of H₂L reveals certain interesting features. Ni(L)²⁺ show two intense electronic bands in the visible region (Table 1). These are believed to originate from charge transfer (ct) transitions. The transfer occurs from a filled bonding diimine orbital of the ligand to an empty metal orbital. The reverse ct i.e., transfer from a filled metal orbital to an empty antibonding diimine orbital is observed in the iron(II) complex Fe(H₂L)²⁺ (band at 19,400 cm⁻¹; ε = 6000). On the other hand the cobalt(III) complexes Co(H₂L)³⁺ and Co(L)³⁺ do not show any low energy ct band. Thus the metal→ligand ct state in Fe(H₂L)²⁺ and the ligand→metal ct state in the nickel(IV) complex are relatively close to the respective ground states; in cobalt(III) neither situation exists. This trend is readily rationalized. The metal d orbitals get progressively depressed relative to the ligand orbitals in the isoelectronic series iron(II), cobalt(III) and nickel(IV). Consequently one traverses a metal→ligand ct situation to ligand→metal ct case through an intermediate case where neither applies.

When a ct state is close to the ground state, appreciable ct contribution may be expected to the latter state (symmetry permitting). Such a contribution would decrease the bond order (and hence decrease stretching frequencies) in the diimine fragment either by depopulating a bonding level (ligand→metal ct) or by populating an antibonding level (metal→ligand ct). The following diimine stretching frequency data substantiate the occurrence of ct contributions in the ground states of iron(II) and nickel(IV) complexes: Ni(H₂L)(ClO₄)₂, 1670, 1600; Fe(H₂L)(ClO₄)₂, 1620, 1540; Co(L)(ClO₄)₃, 1650, 1620; Ni(L)(ClO₄)₂, 1610, 1500 cm⁻¹.

C. Proton Dissociation and Redox Equilibria

Having achieved the goal of obtaining stable nickel(II) and nickel(IV) species, the next logical step was to study acid-base and redox equilibria involving these species. The equilibrium constants of proton dissociation processes (2) and (3) were determined from pH-metric titration with alkali.

The values are pK₁ = 5.90 ± 0.05 and pK₂ = 7.80 ± 0.05 at 25°C. Upto pH 5, Ni(H₂L)²⁺ alone makes major contribution to solution composition while at pH > 8.5 the major species is Ni(L) alone. The intermediate species Ni(HL)⁺ does not play such a singular role except in a very narrow section of pH near 7. For completeness we restate that the nickel(IV) species exists only in the deprotonated form Ni(L)²⁺ even in strongly acidic solutions.

The potential of the couple (4) which will be called couple A was determined (pH < 5) by using the classical potentiometric null method (Pt electrode).

The potential E of this couple is given by (at 25°C)

$$E = E_{2/0}^0 + 0.0295 [\log(p/q) - 2pH] \quad \dots(5)$$

where p and q are respectively the concentrations of Ni(L)²⁺ and Ni(H₂L)²⁺ and E_{2/0}⁰ is the formal electrode potential. The ratio p/q and pH were varied over a considerable range. The observed E varied in a manner such that E_{2/0}⁰ remained constant at 0.70 ± 0.01 V. This and all other potentials reported in this work are referenced to saturated calomel electrode (*see*).

D. Design of Cyclic Voltammeter

Static experiments of the above type are silent on important questions such as the following. Are the two electrons in couple A added in one step or are they added step by step (the later alternative implicating that a nickel(III) intermediate exists)? How fast is the

electron transfer reaction? To answer such questions one has to use a dynamic method such as a cyclic voltammetry¹⁷. Since the necessary equipment is not manufactured in India, we undertook the task of fabricating an inexpensive but accurate cyclic voltammeter using indigenous components¹⁸.

The potentiostatic circuit was designed using opamps SMC 741 (Semiconductors, India) in which the controller amplifier controls the potential in the negative feedback configuration¹⁹. To compensate for the charging current two three-electrode cells (one having only supporting electrolyte; the other having electroactive substance in supporting electrolyte) of same design are used. While the potential of both the cells are controlled by the same potentiostat, the working electrodes are connected to separate current followers. The outputs of these current followers are used as inputs to a subtractor which gives an output (contribution of current from the electroactive species) to be recorded.

The function generator which provides triangular waves was fabricated using the basic circuit of Myers and Shain²⁰ with a few modifications¹⁸ so as to accommodate indigenous components. The unit can produce ramp and hold signals, single cycle and multicycle triangular waves with independently selectable initial potential, anodic and cathodic limit potentials and hold potential.

The working electrode and the counter electrode were made of high-purity platinum wires (0.05 cm diameter). A saturated calomel electrode was used as the reference electrode. The cell container is a double-walled cylindrical glass vessel with inlet and outlet for thermostating purposes. For wire electrodes the diffusion process is cylindrical. The mathematical equations pertaining to cyclic voltammetry become simple when planar electrodes (linear diffusion) are used¹⁷. It was however shown²¹ that at relatively high scan rates the peak positions for the two types of diffusion are the same. We have thoroughly checked¹⁸ that this is so in our experimental set-up at and above the scan rate of 0.01 Vs⁻¹.

E. Coupled Electron Transfer and Proton Transfer

The electrode reaction (4) is but one example of the more general reaction (6) in which all charges except that on

the proton are omitted for clarity. It can be shown¹² that in well-buffered media the relation (7) holds for couple (6).

$$E_{2^{\circ}98}^{\circ} = \bar{E}_p + 0.059(m/n)pH \quad \text{.....(7)}$$

where

$$\bar{E}_p = 0.5 (E_{pc} + E_{pa}) \quad \text{.....(8)}$$

The quantities E_{pc} and E_{pa} are respectively the cyclic voltammetric cathodic and anodic peak potentials. In the particular case where protons are not involved ($m=0$) in the electrode reaction, the special form of Eq. (7) is

$$E_{2^{\circ}98}^{\circ} = \bar{E}_p \quad \text{..... (9)}$$

From Eq. (7) it is readily seen that

$$m = -(n/0.059) (\Delta \bar{E}_p / \Delta pH) \quad \text{..... (10)}$$

where $\Delta \bar{E}_p$ is the shift of \bar{E}_p due to the change in pH by ΔpH . Equation (10) provides a method for determination of m if n is known. Once m becomes known, $E_{2^{\circ}98}^{\circ}$ is readily determined from Eq. (7).

Coupled electron and proton transfer reactions of type (6) are of vital import²² in chemistry and biochemistry. Of particular interest is the situation where a transition metal ion is bound to ligand sites which also hold dissociable protons. A redox transformation of the metal ion naturally affects the pK of the protons. The more oxidized the metal, the less tightly are the protons held. Loss of electrons and protons may thus occur simultaneously. Cyclic voltammetric study of Ni(L)²⁺ and Ni(H₂L)²⁺ reveals model examples of this situation.

F. Cyclic Voltammetry of Nickel System

As stated earlier (Section C) the nickel(II) species exist solely as Ni(H₂L)²⁺ upto pH 5. Starting either with the nickel(II) or the nickel(IV) species a single step voltammogram is observed (Figure 1) at pH < 5. The separation (ΔE_p) between cathodic and anodic peaks lie in the range 30-40 mV (Table 2). This establishes²³ the presence of a reversible one-step two-electron transfer process. The reversibility of the process is maintained upto a scan rate of 0.14 Vs⁻¹. Beyond this progressive irreversibility sets in. The two electron involvement is fully corroborated by constant potential coulometric studies. The peak potentials and hence \bar{E}_p values are pH-dependent showing that protons are involved in the electrode process. Using Eq. (10) and $n=2$, the results yield $m=1$. The electrode reaction is thus (4) i.e. couple A. The $E_{2^{\circ}98}^{\circ}$ values were computed using Eq. (7) (Table 2). The agreement between results obtained by using the null method (Section C) and the cyclic voltammetric method is perfect.

Just above pH 5, ΔE_p begins to increase. By pH 6, couple A is replaced by two distinct reversible ($\Delta E_p = 60 - 70$ mV) couples each of which involves an one-electron step (Figure 1). The peak potentials of the couple at higher potential (couple B) remains invariant with pH. On the other hand the peaks of the couple at lower potential (couple C) undergo progressive cathodic shift with increase of pH till pH ~ 8.5 is reached. Beyond this little further change is observed. This limiting state of couple C will be designated as

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of Ni(H₂L)(ClO₄)₂

couple D. The electrode reactions involved can be identified as :

The E₂₉₈⁰ values of these couples are respectively 0.42, 0.64 and 0.15 V (Table 2). Although not seen

TABLE 2—CYCLIC VOLTAMMETRIC DATA (298°K)

pH	Couple	E _p ⁰ (V)	ΔE _p (V)	E ₂₉₈ ⁰ (V)
1.15	A	0.640	0.030	0.71
2.95	A	0.530	0.040	0.71
4.10	A	0.468	0.035	0.71
7.55	B	0.420	0.060	0.42
	C	0.198	0.070	0.64
9.00	B	0.420	0.070	0.42
	D	0.145	0.070	0.15

directly in the cyclic voltammetric experiment it is possible to show indirectly that the couple E

The reason why the two one-electron couples B and C (or D) become a single two-electron couple A at low pH can be understood on the basis of the expected (and observed) greater proton affinity of Ni(L) compared to Ni(L)⁺ and Ni(L)²⁺. As the pH is lowered Ni(L) goes to Ni(HL)⁺ and finally to Ni(H₂L)²⁺ while the nickel(III) and nickel(IV) species are still unprotonated. The E_p⁰ of couple C consequently shifts progressively towards the unaffected E_p⁰ of couple B as the pH decreases (Eq. (7)). Superposition occurs at pH 5 and beyond this only a single two-electron step is possible. The arguments used here are based on one general

principle ; as more and more electrons are added to a substrate, the proton affinities of the reduced products increase progressively.

G. Separation of Electron Transfer and Proton Transfer Contributions

In equilibria of type (6) electrons and protons are simultaneously involved. It is of considerable interest to see whether the observed thermodynamics of such equilibria can be reconstructed from the thermodynamics of two separate equilibria, one involving only electron transfer and the other involving only proton transfer. These equilibria are

If the standard free energy change in (6) can be written as the sum of the free energy changes in (15) and (16), it is readily derived that Eq. (17) should hold at 298°K :

E₂₉₈⁰ = (E₂₉₈⁰)_e + (0.059/n)pK (17)

Here E₂₉₈⁰ and (E₂₉₈⁰)_e refer respectively to equilibria (6) and (15) and K is the inverse of the equilibrium constant of reaction (16). In the specific cases of equilibria (12) and (14) pK can be expressed respectively as pK₂ and pK₁ + pK₂ (Eqs. (2) and (3)). The values of E₂₉₈⁰ calculated from Eq. (17) using experimental values of (E₂₉₈⁰)_e and pK for the nickel (III)-nickel (II) systems are set out in Table 3. The agreement between experimental and calculated values of E₂₉₈⁰ is excellent. Using similar principles it is also possible to calculate E₂₉₈⁰ for the nickel(IV)-nickel(II) couple (4). Here again the agreement is very good. The separation of total free energy reactions of type (6) into electron transfer and proton transfer contributions is thus valid.

TABLE 3—ELECTRON TRANSFER AND PROTON TRANSFER CONTRIBUTIONS

Couple	Electron transfer	Proton transfer	E ₂₉₈ ⁰ (V)	
			Calcd.	Found
D	0.15	—	—	0.15
C	0.15	0.46	0.61	0.63
E	0.15	0.81	0.96	1.01
A	0.29	0.41	0.70	0.71

H. Evidence for Nickel(III).

In couples (11) – (14) the nickel (III) species Ni(L)⁺ is involved. This does not appear to be stable in solution. Oxidation of Ni(H₂L)(ClO₄)₂ with (NH₄)₂S₂O₈ yields a black solid of composition Ni : ligand : ClO₄ = 1 : 1 : 2. The solid is paramagnetic (1.6–2.3 BM), the exact magnetic moment depending on the conditions of preparation. Every one of the polycrystalline preparations gave the same strong epr signals characteristic^{3,4} of axially symmetric S=1/2 species. The

values are : $g_{\parallel} = 2.04$ and $g_{\perp} = 2.16$ ($g_{av} = 2.12$). While the solids are almost certainly mixtures, it is also certain that they contain a substantial amount of nickel(III) presumably in the form, $Ni(HL)(ClO_4)_2$ which produces the characteristic epr signals.

I. Systems Based on Tridentate Ligands.

The interesting results obtained with the chelates of H_2L prompted us to explore the behaviour of closely related tridentate donor system III. For brevity this discussion will be limited to the specific case of $R = R' = Me$. This ligand will be abbreviated as HT. The syntheses and general physical properties of $Ni(HT)_2(ClO_4)_2$ and $Ni(T)_2(ClO_4)_2$ are closely alike to those of the hexadentate systems. Evidently the coordination sphere IV is involved. Compared to $Ni(H_2L)^{2+}$, $Ni(HT)_2^{2+}$ has slightly lower ($\sim 50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$)

Dq , is much less stable in acidic solution ($pH < 5$) and is a weaker protonic acid ($pK_1 = 7.0$; $pK_2 = 10.00$). A single hexadentate ligand binds nickel(II) more compactly than two tridentate ligands.

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of $Ni(T)_2(ClO_4)_2$

The cyclic voltammetric pattern of the tridentate system in acidic solution is complicated by the decomposition of the nickel(II) species. The height of the anodic peak is negligible compared to that of the cathodic peak at $298^\circ K$; at $283^\circ K$ it is more prominent (Figure 2). From considerations of ΔE_p , pH -dependence and other factors of the electrode reaction is identified as

This is followed by the irreversible decomposition

The E_{298}^0 of the couple (18) is found (from cyclic voltammetric data) to be $0.71 \pm 0.01 \text{ V}$ which is identical to the E_{298}^0 value of couple (4). The tridentate and hexadentate systems produce nickel(IV) species of equal oxidizing power in acidic solutions.

The rate constant k_f of reaction (19) can be determined²³ using cyclic voltammetric results. The parameters involved are r and t where r is the ratio of anodic and cathodic peak currents and t is the time in seconds from \bar{E}_p . The experimental results yield $k_f = 0.16 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at $283^\circ K$ (Table 4)

TABLE 4—RATE CONSTANT FOR DECOMPOSITION OF $Ni(HT)_2^{2+}$ at $283^\circ K$

pH	$v(\text{Vs}^{-1})$	$t(\text{s})$	r	$k_f(\text{s}^{-1})$
1.75	0.010	5.70	0.536	0.15
2.35	0.022	3.81	0.582	0.18
3.75	0.066	1.50	0.802	0.15

In alkaline pH , the decomposition of nickel(II) species is arrested and two distinct one electron couples are observed (Figure 2) as in the case of the hexadentate system. The couples

and

have E_{298}^0 values of 0.39 and 0.66 V respectively. The proton independent nickel(III)-nickel(II) couple

is expected (on the basis of the pK values of $Ni(HT)_2^{2+}$) to become observable at $pH > 10.5$. However at such high pH , irreversible cyclic voltammograms are observed. These could not be interpreted properly.

J. Concluding Remarks

It is convincingly demonstrated that with proper choice of the ligand frame, it is possible to obtain stable salts of nickel(IV) quite easily. The oximate

group plays an extremely important role in this phenomenon of stabilization of high oxidation states possibly by decreasing the effective positive charge on the central metal ion. Thus the ligand system V (compared with I) readily gives nickel(II) complexes but not nickel(IV) species. We have reasons to suspect that the oximate frame (M-N-O) also provides the pathway for electron

transfer reactions to occur. The reversibility of the electrochemical reactions suggest that this pathway is facile and that the stereochemistries of the various nickel(II, III, IV) species are essentially the same (structural type II and IV). One major feature of the present work is the unequivocal characterization of coupled electron transfer proton transfer reactions. Since the thermodynamics of these reactions can be reproduced from the thermodynamics of separate electron transfer and proton transfer steps, it may not be appropriate to call such reactions as "concerted"—a term which has been loosely used in the literature^{2,2}. Lastly we wish to note that formal potential data for couples involving various oxidation states of nickel are very few in literature. The accurate formal potentials reported in this paper are to be viewed in this perspective.

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